
THE ANALYSIS OF SARCASM IN THE MOVIE JOKER WITH SALVATORE ATTARDO THEORY

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ABSTRACT: This research is entitled “The Analysis of Sarcasm in the Movie Joker with Salvatore Attardo Theory”. This research analyzed the types of sarcasm, how the types of sarcasm described, and the dominant type of sarcasm was used in the utterances in the movie Joker. In this research, the researcher used the theory by Salvatore Attardo to classify the types of sarcasm. Within this research, the researcher found 30 data sarcastic utterances and used the descriptive qualitative method to analyze the data. The analysis shows there are 6 types of sarcasm found in the movie Joker, namely there is 30% (9 data) are Evaluation sarcasm, 20% (6 data) are Group Affiliation sarcasm, 16.7% (5 data) are Sophistication sarcasm, 13.3% (4 data) are Retract Ability sarcasm, 10% (3 data) are Politeness sarcasm, and 10% (3 data) are Persuasive Aspect sarcasm. Based on the analysis, the most common type of sarcasm found in the movie Joker is Evaluation sarcasm with 30%. The reason for the evaluation sarcasm as the most common type of sarcasm is to evaluate the situation at that time.

KEYWORDS: Sarcasm, Joker Movie, Salvatore Attardo

INTRODUCTION

Language is the important thing to communicate with other people, exchange ideas, knowledge, thanks, command, help, and feelings between people in our daily life. “Languages provide a variety of ways of saying the same thing, addressing and greeting others, describing things, paying compliments” (Holmes, 2001:3). We can express our feelings with language, such as we can smile when we are happy, pleasure and approval. We also can shriek when we fear and anger. Halliday (1978:21) also adds that language has a function to express our participation, as speakers, in the speech situation; the roles we take on ourselves and impose on others; our wishes, feelings, attitudes, and judgments. That is why people can say something to different people in different ways.

Sarcasm refers to the employment of words that mean the alternative to what you want to mention, especially to someone, to indicate irritation, or simply to be funny. According to Camp (2011), sarcasm is treated as the situation of the speaker meaning the opposite of what they say. As an example, saying "they're really on top of things" to explain a bunch of very disorganized individuals is using sarcasm. Most often, sarcasm is biting and intended to cause pain. Irony also can consult with the utilization of words that mean the other than what you want to say; the "they're really on top of things" statement about the very disorganized group of individuals may also be described as an ironic statement. But irony also can seek advice from a situation that's strange or funny because things happen in a way that seems to be the alternative to what you expected; as an example, it's ironic if someone who was raised by professional musicians but who wanted a different quite life then fell soft on with and married an expert musician.

The movie “Joker” with crime, drama, and thriller genres directed by Todd Philips was released on August 31, 2019, and aired in Indonesia on October 2, 2019. The main character in this film is played by Joaquin Phoenix Arthur Fleck. This movie is set in Gotham City in 1981 and is described as being hit by chaos where social inequality is very severe

In this research, the researcher chose the movie Joker because of the sarcasm found used in the conversation among the character. The utterances from the movie provide adequate data for this research. This movie is about a man named Arthur Fleck who had some conditions and work as a clown in Gotham City. The situation in Gotham City is not fine because of the social gap. Because of his condition, Arthur usually gets bullied. His condition became worse when he cannot get any medicine again and got fired from his office. Sooner or later Arthur gets the truth and finally killed people that make him become like him right now. And the woman who he loved is don't love him too, not like his imagination. This is a turning point why Arthur Fleck becomes a “Joker”. The situation at that time also become a reason for the many criticisms from people about the government. In the movie “Joker” some utterances contain sarcasm utterances and that sarcastic utterance that become the data of this research.

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The researcher will analyze the types of sarcasm, how the types of sarcasm describe, and the dominant type of sarcasm using the descriptive qualitative method. The data will be analyzed using the theory of Salvatore Attardo about the types of sarcasm.

METHOD

In this research, the descriptive qualitative method was used by the researcher to analyze the utterances that contain sarcastic utterances in the movie entitled *Joker* (2019). The aim of this research is to find out the types of sarcasm, how the sarcasm describes, and the dominant type of sarcasm used in the movie *Joker*. The data were analyzed in the form of utterances using the theory of Salvatore Attardo. The researcher analyzed every character in the movie *Joker*. The data were taken from the movie *Joker* directed by Todd Philips which first aired on August 31, 2019. The movie is based on the villain character in the DC comics named Joker. the genre of this movie is thriller, drama, and crime.

In collecting the data, the researcher watched the movie on the HBO platform. Then the researcher downloads the subtitle on the internet. After that the researcher compared the utterances and the script, then the researcher identified the utterances containing sarcastic utterances and classified the types of sarcasm using the table.

In analyzing the data, first, the researcher watched the movie and read the script. Second, the researcher identified the character utterances that contain sarcastic utterances. Third, the researcher classified the sarcastic utterance to each type of sarcasm using a table based on the theory of Salvatore Attardo (2001). Then the researcher explained the type of sarcasm, and describe how the sarcasm in the movie *Joker* as the dominant type of sarcasm. Last, the researcher gains a conclusion based on the result of this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

The data of this research were taken from the utterances in the movie *Joker* .in analyzing and classified the data, the researcher used the theory of Salvatore Attardo (2001) about the types of sarcasm.

The data analysis shows that there are 6 types of sarcasm found in the data. The types of sarcasm are group affiliation, sophistication, evaluation, politeness, persuasuve aspect and retract ability.

Table 1. Sarcasm Utterances In The Movie Joker

Types of Sarcasm	Number of Data	Percentage (%)
Evaluation	9	30.00
Group Affiliation	6	20.00
Sophistication	5	16.70
Retract Ability	4	13.30
Politeness	3	10.00
Persuasive Aspect	3	10.00
Total	30	100.00

From Table 3.1 (Findings of Sarcasm Utterances In The Movie Joker) the utterances that can be classified as sarcastic utterances in the movie *Joker* are 30 utterances. They are also classified into 6 types of sarcastic utterances based on the theory of Salvatore Attardo, as follows: 9 (30%) sarcasm as evaluation, 6 (20%) sarcasm as group affiliation, 5 (16.7%) sarcasm as sophistication, 4 (13.3%) sarcasm as retract ability, 3 (10%) sarcasm as politeness and 3 (10%) sarcasm as persuasive aspect.

Discussion

Based on the data analysis, the researcher discussed the types of sarcasm utterances that found in utterances in the movie *Joker* and the dominant type of sarcasm that used in the movie *Joker*. The researcher found 6 types of sarcasm in the movie *Joker*. The discussion is shown as follows:

Evaluation Sarcasm

Excerpt 1

Murray: "So, I know you're a comedian. You been working on any new material? You wanna tell us a joke?"

Arthur: "Yeah? Okay."

Murray: "He's got a book. A book of jokes. **Take your time. We got all night.**"

It used by the speaker to evaluation the hearer that he used a book to make a joke while he was a comedian. The speaker don't think that a comedian need to read a book of joke to tell the joke what they made. This utterance as evaluation sarcasm because the speaker evaluating the hearer's action of take a book before making a joke.

Group Affiliation Sarcasm

Excerpt 2

Randall: "Do you people call it miniature golf or it is just golf **to you?**"

Based on the utterance above, the speaker used word "to you" to express the different the hearer with the other people. The hearer has some condition that he is stunted. This utterance as a group affiliation sarcasm because it divided the hearer and the speaker.

Sophistication Sarcasm

Excerpt 3

Gigi's mother: "I think the guy that did it is a hero. Three less pricks in Gotham City, only a million more to go."

Based on the utterance above, the speaker used word "a million" to reveal her true feeling about the news that three people have been killed by someone. This is consider as sophistication sarcasm because the speaker used figurative language to express her feeling.

Retract Ability Sarcasm

Excerpt 4

Gigi's mother: "I thought that was you. **I was hoping you'd come in and rob the place.**"

Arthur: "I have a gun. I could come by tomorrow."

Gigi's mother: "You're so funny, Arthur."

The utterance is used to express that the speaker probably need someone to rob the place. It can be classified as retract ability sarcasm because the speaker in the fact don't want someone to rob the place because that place is her office.

Politeness Sarcasm

Excerpt 5

Psikiater: "How does it feel to have to come here? Does it help to have someone to talk to?"

Arthur: "**I think** I felt better when I was locked up in the hospital."

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The speaker used the utterance to give less aggressive to the hearer. It is politeness sarcasm because the speaker used phrase “I think” than used “I don’t feel better” to give less damage to the hearer.

Persuasive Aspect Sarcasm

Excerpt 6

Man 1: “Did you really bring a gun to the children's hospital, Artie? What the fuck would you do that for?”

Man 3: “Is that part of your new act, Arthur?”

If your dancing doesn't do the trick, you're just gonna shoot yourself?”

Arthur: “**Why don’t you ask Randall about it?**”

The speaker used word “why” to make the hearer thinking about what is the real. This utterance is persuasive aspect because the speaker make the hearer believe what the truth.

Evaluation Sarcasm as the Dominant Type of Sarcasm in the Movie Joker

In the movie Joker, the researcher found 9 data (30%) of sarcasm utterances that contain evaluation sarcasm, meanwhile, the rest of the data (70%) contains group affiliation sarcasm, sophistication sarcasm, politeness sarcasm, and persuasive aspect sarcasm, and retract ability sarcasm.

As already described in the background, the movie’s setting is 1981, where at that time in Britain, people were not satisfied with the existing government. The social gap between the rich and the poor people getting further. In the movie Joker, evaluation sarcasm is dominantly used because of criticism about the situation at that time and also criticism about the people’s action and the government.

Excerpt

Arthur: “... when you cross a mentally-ill loner with a society that abandons him like him a trash?”

Based on the expert above, the speaker also gave criticism to all people that ignore or do not care about someone with a special condition. In that movie, people usually act like don’t see what happened to the people with the special condition they don’t want to help them even if they are in trouble, also they even make fun of people with special conditions. Also at that time, the government don’t take care of people with special conditions, they even repeal subsidies from an institution that took care of them and give them medicine.

The reason evaluation sarcasm is the biggest type of sarcasm used in the movie *Joker* is trying to criticize the government’s decision, the rich people want to satisfy themselves, people behavior toward people with special conditions, etc. This is also evaluated to the situation at that time i.e 1981 people racist to other ethnic, high crime rate, unsatisfied people with the government, and anything else.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings in this research, the researcher found six types of sarcasm that used in the utterances in the movie Joker. The types of sarcasm are 9 data (30%) of Evaluation Sarcasm, 6 data (20%) of Group Affiliation Sarcasm, 5 data (16.7%) of Sophistication Sarcasm, 4 data (13.3%) of Retract Ability Sarcasm, 3 data (10%) of Politeness Sarcasm and 3 data (10%) of Persuasive Aspect Sarcasm.

In the movie Joker, the sarcastic utterances are realized through context and intended meaning of by the speaker to the hearer. The sarcastic utterances can be realized by sarcastically evaluate someone the hearer’s state or behavior, playing with language to indirectly express the speaker’s feeling, commanding the hearer to believe or do something by the hearer, dividing people into a group standard or value, used some word that not fit with the world or reality, and using less damage to the hearer.

Based on the data and the analysis of sarcasm utterances in the movie Joker, the dominant type of sarcasm used in the movie is evaluation sarcasm. According to Salvatore Attardo (2001: 183) evaluation sarcasm is a type of sarcasm that can mute the negative effects of criticism also at the same time can mute the positive effects of praise. In the movie Joker, the researcher found nine sarcasm utterances that contain evaluation sarcasm. As already described in the background that the movie’s setting is 1981, where at that time in Britain, people are not satisfied with the existing government.

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The social gap between the rich and the poor people getting further. In the movie Joker, evaluation sarcasm is dominantly used because of criticism about the situation at that time and also criticism about the people's actions and the government. The reason evaluation sarcasm is the biggest type of sarcasm used in the movie Joker is trying to criticize the government's decision, the rich people want to satisfy themselves, people behavior toward people with special conditions, etc. This is also an evaluation of the situation at that time i.e 1981 people were racist toward other ethnic, high crime rate, unsatisfied people with the government, etc.

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